

TRANSFER LEARNING STRATEGIES FOR OPTIMISING FACIAL RECOGNITION ACCURACY

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ABSTRACT

Human-computer interaction relies heavily on facial emotion recognition (FER), yet creating reliable models is difficult because of inter-subject variability and a lack of personalised data. In this study, we offer a method for improving the accuracy of face recognition with convolutional neural networks (CNNs) that is based on transfer learning. Initially, a generic model is trained using the massive AffectNet dataset; next, it is fine-tuned using the smaller AMIGOS dataset, which contains subject-specific data. The solution is aimed at one-dimensional emotion prediction (valence and arousal) and the Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) of 0.09 and 0.10, respectively. In addition, testing is done for alternative methods of data sampling active and passive to use and to minimize the cost of labelling and accuracy by using greedy sampling and Monte Carlo Dropout Uncertainty Estimation. This approach offers a scalable, efficient solution for personalised FER systems with real-world applications in psychological health monitoring, adaptive interfaces as well as affect-aware computing. The results demonstrate that only 20-30% of labelled personal data is adequate for near-optimal performance.

Keywords: *Facial Recognition, Transfer Learning, Valence, Arousal, Convolution Neural Network, Deep Learning*

1. INTRODUCTION

In applications ranging from healthcare and affective computing to security surveillance and e-learning platforms, facial recognition systems have become essential components of contemporary HCI, allowing for intuitive and non-invasive comprehension of user states [1], [2], [3]. FER is one of several applications of face analysis that is attracting a lot of interest because of its potential to help machines understand and respond to emotions, provide more tailored user experiences, and improve machine empathy. Use cases such as affective user interfaces, cognitive

load evaluation, and mental health monitoring necessitate facial expression recognition for emotions [4], [5].

Conventional FER systems mostly used hand-crafted visual characteristics like Local Binary Patterns (LBP), Histogram of Oriented Gradients (HOG), or Facial Action Units (FAUs) to categorise emotions; these included happy, sad, furious, and shocked [6], [7]. These traditional methods frequently used shallow classifiers like k-Nearest Neighbours (k-NN) and Support Vector Machines (SVMs). Due to considerable inter-subject variability, illumination variations, head positions, occlusions, and a lack of labelled data,

these systems performed much worse in real-world settings even if they showed respectable accuracy under restricted circumstances.

In response to these shortcomings, recent years have also seen an emergence of deep learning techniques, especially Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) that have the potential to directly learn hierarchical spatial features of an image directly with no manual process of engineering features involved [8], [9], [10]. The CNN-based models have shown the best results of FER tasks as long as trained on big datasets either AffectNet, FER2013 or emotioNet. Yet, training deep CNNs in an end-to-end fashion requires substantial amount of labeled data and computational resources, which are not satisfied in the setting of personalized applications as only a small amount of user-specific data exists [11].

In addition, rather than utilising discrete categories to describe human emotional states, the dimensional model provides a more complex picture by characterising emotions using continuous scales like valence (the degree of positivity) and arousal (the degree of intensity). Improved modelling of complicated emotional events and more seamless emotion transitions are both made possible by ongoing annotations provided by valence and arousal ratings [12], [13], [14]. Due to the subjective nature of emotional intensities and the difficulty in accurately annotating them across people, regression-based FER systems have additional difficulties in data labelling.

Transfer learning has become a potential way to deal with these problems in FER and other visual tasks that are similar. Transfer learning lets you use models that have already been trained on large, broad datasets for tasks that use smaller, more specific datasets in the future. These models can use learned representations to improve learning efficiency, speed up convergence, and improve generalisation by moving knowledge from a general domain (source) to a personalised or restricted domain (target) [15], [16], [17].

In this study we present a subject-specific, transfer learning based, facial emotion recognition system utilizing CNNs where we hope to use a base model, trained on a large general-purpose dataset (AffectNet) and fine tune it on small subject specific data provided by AMIGOS dataset [18], [19]. The main objective is to maximize the accuracy of facial emotion recognition per user, and consequently, reduce the number of labeled personal data that must be used. We are concerned with the prediction of valence and arousal values in

line with the dimensions of emotion model [20], [21].

The threefold contributions are 1) One transfer of learning approach to personalization: We show that a CNN trained on AffectNet then fine-tuned on even small splits of the AMIGOS data dataset can achieve a relatively unknown RMSE much lower than comparable training-from-scratch models and similar RMSE on valence and arousal. 2) Sampling Strategy Evaluation: We would further lower the labelling requirement by considering some active and passive sampling methods (e.g. random sampling, greedy sampling, Monte Carlo Dropout Uncertainty Estimation) to sample the most informative examples within the user dataset. 3) Empirical Insights: Experimentally, we can characterize the performance trends, so that a plateau in performance increments is observed and documented to be around 20-30% of training data, and that the valence had better generalization properties within the subjects against the arousal counterpart, and how this can be used to refine future models.

The remaining part of the work is structured like this: In Section 2, we look at relevant research on transfer learning and face emotion identification. Model design, dataset preparation, and training approach are all covered in Section 3 of the methodology. The experimental data and important discoveries are presented and discussed in Section 4. Section 5 wraps up the analysis and provides an outline of potential future research topics.

2. RELATED WORK

The evolution of Facial Emotion Recognition (FER) has been substantial, transitioning from traditional machine learning methods that employed handcrafted features to contemporary deep learning techniques [22]. Conventional FER models frequently employed classifiers such as Support Vector Machines (SVMs) in conjunction with features such as Local Binary Patterns (LBP), Histogram of Oriented Gradients (HOG), and Action Units (AUs). However, these models demonstrate satisfactory performance in controlled environments; however, they encountered difficulties in generalising their capabilities to a variety of facial structures, poses, and illumination conditions. Moreover, the granularity required for nuanced applications is absent in categorical emotion recognition (e.g., joyful, melancholy).

In response to such shortcomings, CNNs (Convolutional Neural Networks) have been

recently used in literature, as they are automatic methods of learning hierarchical spatial features. CNNs example: The CNNs which are trained on large datasets such as FER2013 and AffectNet have shown that such a model can achieve state-of-the-art categorical and dimensional modeling of emotions with continuous valence-arousal scores. As an example, Mollahosseini et al. (2017) trained AlexNet on AffectNet and reported the RMSEs of 0.394 (valence) and 0.402 (arousal) [23]. But these models tend to have poor generalization with non-personalised models across users because of excessive inter-subject variability.

Transfer learning has emerged as a reliable solution for situations with inadequate data. Transfer learning enables rapid convergence and increased accuracy with fewer samples by repurposing knowledge from models that have been pre-trained on large-scale datasets. Feffer & Picard (2018) and Ng et al. (2015) have both shown that the efficacy of pre-trained networks can be significantly improved on small or personalised datasets [24] by fine-tuning, respectively. However, these methods frequently presuppose that each user has access to a significant amount of labelled data. Rescigno et al. (2020) [25] suggested a framework of transfer learning and selective data sampling to deal with the concept of personalization with little data. The manner of their approach optimized the pre-trained AlexNet on the AMIGOS data set and attained RMSEs that were less than 0.10 where they used only 20-30 percent of the labelled data. The work was motivated by this one since it contributed to the extension of its methodology by a rigorous comparison of sampling strategies and the fine-tuning of individual emotion prediction based on both sets of valence and arousal metrics.

The combined effect of personalised fine-tuning & sample-efficient training in dimensional FER has not been thoroughly investigated in much research, despite advances. This study addresses that knowledge gap by investigating scalable solutions for real-world personalised FER systems using CNN-based transfer learning models with different active and passive sampling methodologies.

3. METHODOLOGY

To enhance the accuracy of face emotion identification, the suggested method combines active sampling with personalised fine-tuning and transfer learning. The five components of the methodology outlined in this section are Dataset

preparation, convolutional neural network design, transfer learning framework, fine-tuning technique & sample optimisation.

3.1. Overall Framework

The suggested approach, which maximises face emotion recognition through transfer learning, is divided into three successive steps. In the first step, CNN is pre-trained using AffectNet, a massive, multi-purpose dataset that includes labelled photos of people's faces taken in a variety of natural settings. This is the crucial step that allows CNNs and AlexNet in particular, to acquire strong, generalizable properties for representing emotions. The second step implies that the pre-trained network will be fine-tuned personally using subject-specific data comprising the AMIGOS dataset. The model allows learning the traits of the facial features of the person with fewer training data by only changing the dense layers without freezing the convolutional layers. Gluttony sampling, random sampling & Monte Carlo dropout uncertainty estimation (MCDUE) are some of the sample algorithms included in the last step, which aims to optimise performance is shown in figure 1. To reduce the data labelling load while retaining high model accuracy, these strategies are used to quickly choose the most informative examples for training. The scalability and user-friendliness of the facial recognition system are guaranteed by this framework.

Figure 1 Transfer learning workflow

3.2. Dataset Preparation

The source dataset was AffectNet used as pre-training and the target dataset was used by AMIGOS which involved individualised fine-tuning. Both significant datasets served differently as far as preparation of the dataset is concerned.

3.2.1. Source Dataset: affectnet

More than a million face photos are gathered from the internet utilising emotion-related search queries, AffectNet is one of the biggest publicly accessible facial expression databases. Over 450,000 of these photos have been hand annotated. Both dimensional emotion qualities, such as valence, which gauges emotional positively & arousal, which gauges emotional intensity, are included in the annotations along with category emotion labels, such as happy, sorrow, rage & fear. The convolutional neural network (CNN) was pre-trained using this annotated subset of AffectNet, which allowed it to learn rich, generalised characteristics linked to facial expressions and emotional signals across a wide range of people.

3.2.2. Target Dataset: AMIGOS

Recordings of forty people' reactions to emotional video stimuli make up the AMIGOS dataset, a multi-modal affective computing resource. A subgroup of ten participants was chosen for this investigation. The study retrieved picture frames from each participant's frontal-view video recordings at a rate of 4 seconds, yielding around 1,000 frames per subject. The remaining photos were given valence and arousal levels after manually removing frames with undesirable features (such as occlusions or turned faces). To guarantee accuracy and consistency, these labels were determined by averaging the scores of three professional annotators. To make the pre-trained CNN more adaptable to unique face traits with less training data, this processed dataset was then utilised for fine-tuning as shown in figure 2.

Figure 2 Preprocessing pipeline

3.3. CNN Architecture: Alexnet Modification

The study used AlexNet architecture for face emotion identification because it is efficient and performs well in picture classification tasks,

especially ones that include face images. The pretraining details are given in table 1. To provide non-linearity and speed up training convergence, AlexNet uses Rectified Linear Unit (ReLU) activation functions in each of its five convolutional layers. Max pooling is applied after the first, second and the fifth convolutional layers, to squeeze out the most significant characteristics and reduce the number of spatial dimensions progressively. After the convolutional blocks, the network has three fully connected (FC) layers that convert the features that were recovered into representations that are appropriate for regression tasks. To train AlexNet to estimate emotions in the dimensional model, we switched out the network's multi-class output neurone for a single linear output neurone in the network's final output layer, which was originally built for multi-class classification. This allowed the network to handle regression instead of classification. So that each emotional dimension could be trained specifically for its own purpose, two networks were created and trained separately: one to predict emotional valence (positive feeling) and another to predict emotional arousal (intensity) as shown in figure 3.

Table 1 Training details for pretraining

Parameter	Value
Optimizer	Mini-Batch Gradient Descent (MBGD)
Batch size	16
Learning rate	0.001
Momentum	0.9 (Nesterov)
Epochs	50
Loss function	Mean Squared Error (MSE)

Figure 3 AlexNet architecture with regression head for dimensional emotion prediction

3.4. Transfer Learning and Fine-Tuning Strategy

A transfer learning strategy that puts an emphasis on selective model adaptation to successfully customise the pre-trained convolutional neural network (CNN) for specific users with minimal data needs is implemented. To be more precise, the CNN's convolutional layers are frozen after training them on the massive AffectNet dataset. All topics can still benefit from these layers' general-purpose visual feature extraction capabilities. Subsequently, subject-specific data from the AMIGOS dataset was used to fine-tune just the fully connected (dense) layers that remained trainable. While maintaining the strength of the previously learnt features, this method enables the network to acquire personal traits pertinent to emotion identification. This method diminishes computational complexity, speeds up training convergence, and reduces the risk of overfitting by restricting updates to the dense layers, due to the lack of individual-specific labelled data as shown in figure 4.

Figure 4 Transfer Learning strategies for emotion identification

3.5. Sampling Optimisation Techniques

The identification and selection of the most informative samples for fine-tuning are imperative due to the limited availability of subject-specific labelled data. Efficient sampling procedures may reduce the annotation effort while preserving or even improving model performance.

To optimise the training process, we investigate and contrast four sampling techniques: Monte Carlo Dropout Uncertainty Estimation (MCDUE), enhanced greedy sampling (iGS), greedy sampling (GSx and GSy), and random sampling.

3.5.1. Random sampling

The standard method is based on random sampling. This technique uses a pool of subject-specific data to randomly choose training samples. Random sampling fails to capitalise on an understanding of the data distribution and model uncertainty, despite its computational simplicity and affordability. Suboptimal in situations with limited labelling expenditures, it may comprise samples that are redundant or do not provide useful information.

3.5.2. Greedy Sampling (gsx, gsy)

The purpose of greedy sampling is to increase the variety of chosen samples in the output or feature space. The GSx variation uses Euclidean distance

to find samples that are the furthest from previously labelled locations while it explores the input feature space. This improves generalizability by guaranteeing that recently added samples offer unique properties to the training set.

GSy, on the other hand, looks at the output space and figures out distances using the model's expected outputs, like valence/arousal scores. GSy helps the model learn emotional patterns that aren't shown enough by giving more weight to samples whose output values are different from the labels on current examples.

Consideration of both input and output distances results in taking the best of both worlds by merging GSx and GSy: the iGS (improved Greedy Sampling) approach. A more informative and balanced training sub-set can be created through finding examples that are simultaneously diverse in feature representation and prediction space.

3.5.3. Monte carlo dropout uncertainty Estimation

As an active learning method, MCDUE uses the unpredictability of model predictions to direct the selection of samples. It uses a regularisation technique called Monte Carlo dropout, which applies dropout both during training and inferences. The model is iterated with varying numbers of randomly discarded units for each input sample (e.g., 50 iterations). An indicator of how uncertain the model is for that sample is the standard deviation (STD) of the forecasts that emerge from it.

Priority is given to labelling and adding samples to the fine-tuning set based on their highest STD, which indicates the highest level of uncertainty. By helping the model concentrate on unclear or poorly understood data points, this technique improves generalisation and speeds up learning convergence while using fewer training examples as shown in table 2.

From the most basic (random) to the most advanced (GS and MCDUE) possibilities, these sampling approaches cover all possibilities when it comes to training optimisation. In the result section, we compare their efficacy using controlled experiments with different sizes of training sets.

Table 2 Algorithm Pseudocode

Technique	Description
GSx	Chooses samples farthest from labeled set in feature space.
GSy	Uses initial regression model to guide output-space exploration.
iGS	Combines GSx and GSy distances.
MCDUE	Picks samples with highest standard deviation in dropout predictions.

3.6. Evaluation Metrics

The Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE) was the primary measure that the regression models that tried to predict the emotional features of emotion and arousal were judged. When it comes to affective computing jobs with real-valued outputs, root-mean-squared error (RMSE) is a commonly used metric for assessing the precision of continuous forecasts. It measures how far off the actual ground-truth annotations are from the model's outputs in terms of prediction errors; lower numbers indicate better performance. The root-mean-squared error (RMSE) provides a strong picture of prediction quality as it punishes bigger mistakes more severely than smaller ones, making it ideal for this application.

A group of 10 unique participants from the AMIGOS dataset was subjected to 5-fold cross-validation in our experimental setup to guarantee the generality and consistency of results. To report the average RMSE across all folds, the dataset was divided into training and verification subsets for each fold.

The RMSE is mathematically defined as

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (\hat{y}_i - y_i)^2}$$

Here y_i denotes the actual valence or arousal value, \hat{y}_i is the predicted value by the model and n is the total number of samples. This metric provides a direct and interpretable measure of prediction error, making it ideal for evaluating regression-based emotion recognition systems.

4. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The experimental results of the suggested transfer learning framework for face emotion identification are detailed here. This includes a comparison of various training environments and sampling techniques. Separate analyses of valence and arousal are conducted on the results, shedding light on the effects of data sampling and transfer learning on the performance of the models. After applying 5-fold cross-validation to 10 participants from the AMIGOS dataset, we averaged the findings using Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE).

4.1. Impact Of Transfer Learning

Three different training setups were tested to assess the efficacy of transfer learning in face emotion identification. The convolutional neural network (CNN) was trained completely from scratch using solely subject-specific input in the first configuration, known as No Transfer, without using any past information. This environment provided a starting point for evaluating the effectiveness of customised models created without the use of generalised characteristics. A CNN pre-trained on the extensive AffectNet dataset was used in the second configuration, designated Transfer Only (0% labelling). It was then tested immediately on the target subject's data without any further fine-tuning. The capacity of generalised representations to forecast emotional aspects without personalisation was assessed using this method. Lastly, the pre-trained CNN was further refined utilising the whole labelled dataset of the target subject in the third configuration, which is referred to as Transfer + Fine-Tuning (100% labelling). This configuration was created to quantify the extra advantage of using supervised learning to modify the generalised model to match unique facial features. When combined, these settings allowed for a thorough evaluation of the contributions made to model correctness by both transferred information and customised fine-tuning. Figure 5 shows that the setup with Transfer + Fine-Tuning had the best RMSE values for valence and arousal.

Figure 5 RMSE comparison across transfer settings for valence and arousal prediction

A pre-trained model combined with personalised data yielded notable benefits, as the root-mean-squared error (RMSE) for valence decreased from 0.37 to 0.09 and for arousal from 0.22 to 0.10. When it came to valence, which seems to be more transferrable between subjects, the Transfer Only configuration likewise fared better than the No Transfer setup. On the other hand, fine-tuning was crucial for arousal prediction since it showed a stronger dependence on individual-specific traits.

4.2. Effect Of Sample Size On Performance

The study raised the proportion of training samples utilised for fine-tuning (from 5% to 90%) gradually to examine the impact of personal data on model accuracy. The RMSE values for every setting were monitored.

Figure 6 RMSE performance with increasing training set size for valence and arousal

The performance peaks at 30% arousal and 20% valence following training with tiny quantities of

data, as seen in Figure 6. The data annotation effort is greatly reduced because only around 240 to 320 labelled samples are enough to obtain near-optimal performance. Since valence shows a more pronounced early performance improvement than arousal, it is reasonable to assume that its representation is less specific and more transferrable.

4.3. Comparison Of Sampling Techniques

Four sample strategies were assessed to reduce the need for substantial human annotation: Monte Carlo Dropout Uncertainty Estimation (MCDUE), Improved Greedy sample (iGS), Random Sampling & Greedy Sampling (including GSx and GSy variations) (Figure 7). 30% of the training data that was available was used for each approach, and the average performance results were obtained for each participant. The goal of this comparison research was to determine the best method for choosing relevant samples to maximise model performance while requiring less work to label data.

Figure 7 RMSE for different sampling techniques at 30% training data

The benefits of using variety in both the feature and output spaces were demonstrated by the slightly improved performance of iGS compared to the other methods. It is surprising that random sampling was competitive, particularly when there was enough data, which implies that sampling technique is more important when there is very little data (e.g., less than 10%).

4.4. Discussion And Interpretation

The outcomes of the experiment demonstrate how well transfer learning and little

subject-specific fine-tuning may increase the accuracy of emotion detection. The key findings are pre-trained models are more beneficial to valence, which is more generalizable. Arousal requires personalisation, which implies that everyone must fine-tune. To get near-maximum performance, you'll need about 240-320 tagged personal samples. Sample optimisation loses some of its effectiveness as the amount of training data increases. The behaviour of the model is consistent with psychological research: arousal varies more among people and situations, but valence is frequently simpler to deduce from facial expressions. Additionally, transfer learning's effectiveness without requiring sizable fine-tuning datasets emphasises the method's usefulness in real-world settings including driver alertness systems, emotion-aware interfaces, and mental health monitoring programmes.

5. CONCLUSION

The transfer learning and individual fine-tuning-based facial emotion recognition (FER) optimisation approach suggested is powerful and timesaving. This is because i) our method uses an existing large data set (AffectNet) and pre-trained network (AlexNet) without any fine-tuning and ii) by using the proposed method, the augmented dataset (pairs of images labelled under valence and arousal) of limited size (20 and 40 images respectively) leads to significant improvement in the accuracy of valence and arousal prediction. The experimental findings indicate that when carrying near-optimal performance, the model uses only 20-30 percent of labelled personal data and yields low RMSE of 0.09 for valence and 0.10 in arousal. Further reduction in data labelling needs may be achieved by intelligent sample selection, as demonstrated by the assessment of several sampling approaches such as greedy, random, as well as Monte Carlo Dropout Uncertainty Estimation (MCDUE). The results show that a scalable and feasible approach for real-world FER systems might be transfer learning with sample optimisation. The goal of future research is to refine this framework so it can be used for real-time emotion identification on edge devices with several modalities.

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